

Simulating Queen Pineapple Supply Chain in Camarines Norte: A Simulation Study Using AnyLogic

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Abstract—This simulation study analyses the supply chain of queen pineapple in Camarines Norte with the use of simulation software AnyLogic utilizing the Agent-Based Modeling (ABM) and Discrete Event Simulation (DES). The study focuses on identifying the inefficiencies in the supply chain and providing data that can help stakeholders propose strategies to enhance the supply chain efficiency and sustainability. Key variables such as production, processing, distribution, pricing, and utilization of pineapples for local and processed products were examined. The simulation revealed that the major contributor to the inefficiency in the supply chain of Queen pineapple in Camarines Norte is the high percentage of harvest loss which affects the potential profits for farmers and the profitability of traders, leading to an imbalance in earnings across the supply chain. Addressing this issue through improved post-harvest handling practices, investment in processing facilities, and the adoption of modern agricultural techniques is recommended. This simulation study contributes to understanding the queen pineapple supply chain in Camarines Norte and offers a replicable framework that can be used for future studies for diagnosing supply chain inefficiencies in other crops. The findings serve as an insight for the stakeholders to implement strategies aimed at improving the livelihood of farmers, optimizing the use of resources, and enhancing the overall quality and sustainability of the supply chain.

Keywords— *supply chain simulation; simulation modeling; queen pineapple; agent-based modeling; discrete event simulation; AnyLogic; post-harvest loss*

I. INTRODUCTION

Pineapples hold a significant place in the agricultural and economic landscape of the Philippines, particularly in the province of Camarines Norte, where the 'Queen' pineapple variety thrives. The industry not only

provides livelihood opportunities to farmers but also contributes to the local economy through domestic and international trade. However, the pineapple supply chain in this region is fraught with challenges, ranging from inefficiencies in post-harvest handling and logistics to market access and socio-economic constraints. These issues culminate in substantial post-harvest losses, reduced farmer incomes, and heightened vulnerabilities within the supply chain ecosystem.

Camarines Norte's pineapple sector exemplifies the intricate dynamics of agricultural value chains in developing regions. Beyond the production process, the supply chain encompasses a network of interconnected activities, stakeholders, and systemic inefficiencies that influence the economic and social outcomes for all involved parties. Previous studies have documented post-harvest losses and analyzed factors affecting farmer productivity, yet there remains a critical need for a comprehensive systems approach that addresses the interdependencies within the supply chain.

According to FAO in 2021 [5], pineapples rank top 3 among the most traded tropical fruits, with increasing demand from health-conscious consumers. Camarines Norte's Queen pineapple holds a unique position due to its distinct sweetness and quality, offering potential for expanding its market value [14]. While existing research has provided insights into individual components of the supply chain, such as production practices and post-harvest losses, a comprehensive perspective that integrates economic, logistical, and socio-environmental dimensions remains underexplored. Addressing this gap is critical for designing interventions that optimize the entire value chain.

However, the pineapple supply chain in Camarines Norte is filled with challenges, ranging from inefficiencies in post-harvest handling and logistics to market access and socio-economic constraints. These issues culminate in substantial post-harvest losses, reduced farmer incomes, and heightened vulnerabilities

within the supply chain ecosystem [15]. Beyond production, the supply chain encompasses a network of interconnected activities, stakeholders, and systemic inefficiencies that influence the economic and social outcomes for all involved parties.

This study aims to fill this gap by analyzing the Queen pineapple supply chain in Camarines Norte, identifying critical aspects, assessing inefficiencies, and proposing actionable strategies for improvement. The findings will provide valuable insights for stakeholders, including farmers, cooperatives, policymakers, and industry players, to enhance supply chain efficiency and sustainability.

Ultimately, this research contributes not only to addressing practical challenges in the pineapple industry but also to advancing the field of supply chain diagnostics and agricultural value chain optimization, providing a replicable framework for other crops in developing regions.

II. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Pineapple Production Challenges and Opportunities

The Queen pineapple, particularly prominent in Camarines Norte, is a high-value crop that contributes significantly to the local economy. However, its production faces challenges such as pest and disease management, post-harvest losses, and market access. Gerance [1] utilized a systems approach to assess post-harvest losses in the Queen pineapple value chain. The study highlighted critical loss points, with post-harvest losses reaching 47.81% due to handling and sorting inefficiencies. It emphasized the need for collaboration among stakeholders and the adoption of post-harvest technologies to mitigate losses.

The application of foliar fertilizers was explored by Obrero and Valencia [2], who investigated their impact on Queen pineapple growth and fruit quality. The study found that foliar fertilizers, such as Sea Crop, could improve the sweetness and yield of pineapples, offering a cost-effective alternative to conventional fertilizers. These findings align with the increasing demand for environmentally sustainable agricultural practices.

Socioeconomic Impacts of Pineapple Farming

Camarines Norte farmers rely heavily on pineapple farming as a source of income. Campita [3] analyzed the socioeconomic characteristics of pineapple farmers, noting that land tenure and access to modern agricultural practices significantly influenced productivity. The study recommended adopting production innovations, including improved land preparation and fertilization techniques, to enhance yields and lift farmers above the poverty threshold.

In addition, Ezaki et al. [4] examined the role of farmers' cooperatives in addressing gender-divide needs in pineapple farming. The research revealed that while men primarily manage production, women play a significant role in post-harvest activities, such as selling and processing. This division underscores the importance of

gender-sensitive interventions to enhance overall productivity and equity in the pineapple value chain.

Post-Harvest Innovations and Market Potential

The development of innovative products like pineapple juice, dried pineapple, and barong fiber from pineapple leaves has been proposed as a strategy to reduce waste and diversify income streams. Obrero and Valencia [2] reported that value-added products could significantly enhance the profitability of smallholder farmers. Similarly, Gerance [1] highlighted the importance of establishing standards for product quality to access high-value markets, both locally and internationally.

To ensure product competitiveness, proper post-harvest handling practices and storage solutions are essential. Campita [3] emphasized the critical role of cold storage and efficient transport systems in reducing spoilage and maintaining fruit quality during distribution.

Agent-Based Modeling and Discrete Event Simulation

The application of Agent-Based Model (ABM) and Discrete Event Simulation (DES) in pineapple agriculture presents a revolutionary method for improving crop health prediction and management through stochastic inference. These models facilitate the identification and diagnosis of pests and diseases, yield prediction, and the optimization of agricultural practices by utilizing historical and real-time data. ABM and DES provide a comprehensive analysis for understanding the Queen pineapple supply chain in Camarines Norte. Additionally, this approach supports the simulation of different agricultural scenarios, allowing for the assessment of potential outcomes and informed decision-making. Adopting this methodology could significantly reduce risks, enhance resource allocation, and promote sustainable agricultural practices, ultimately boosting productivity and resilience in pineapple farming systems.

III. METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The research design for the study will be mixed-methods and systems-oriented. It combines elements of qualitative and quantitative research, with a focus on simulation-based modeling and diagnostics to uncover the root causes of inefficiencies and bottlenecks within the Queen pineapple supply chain by exploring its interconnected stages. This study aims to establish a fundamental understanding of the current supply chain's weaknesses and will serve as a basis for subsequent research.

Utilizing a simulation model will enable a controlled environment to assess the various critical factors such as harvest losses, transport inefficiencies, and cost structures.

The study utilized the Agent-Based Modeling combined with Discrete Event Simulation that is used to

determine the critical aspects and inefficiencies to provide strategies through the use of simulation in the supply chain of Queen pineapple in Camarines Norte. ABM and DES provide useful insights that are used to provide and create strategies for improving the supply chain of Queen pineapple in the province.. The current objectives require a method capable of capturing not only direct relationships but also probabilistic dependencies between variables such as input availability, transport conditions, post-harvest losses, and farmer income. ABM and DES excel in this regard by representing these relationships in a graphical structure that incorporates uncertainty and variability.

Research Instrument

To determine the inefficiencies and create a simulation model for diagnostic analysis the researchers utilized the Agent-Based Modeling and Discrete Event Simulation model in Camarines Norte’s queen pineapple supply chain for several reasons.

Firstly, it aligns with one of the key challenges in supply chain diagnostics which is accounting for the influence of multiple, interconnected factors, many of which are uncertain or random in nature.

For instance, ABM was used for decision-making behaviors of different variables such as farmers and retailers while DES models the processes such as transportation, processing, and distribution. ABM can be used to simulate the behavior of different agent variables and their interactions while DES allows for modeling the important processes over a set period of time. When used simultaneously, ABM and DES provide insights that could help understand the inefficiencies in different areas of the supply chain that can impact the entire chain. This aligns with the goal to provide insights to different stakeholders.

Furthermore, ABM and DES are suitable for conditions where data availability is available but limited. These models provide information on data with expert knowledge to define variables, process flow, and constraints. The simulation is highly useful in developing regions such as Camarines Norte where detailed datasets may not always be available[13].

Data Analysis

In this phase, the scope of the diagnostic supply chain analysis is defined via taking factors such as production, processing, distribution, pricing, and environmental and logistical considerations. The data comprises expert elicitation from agencies handling the Queen pineapple supply chain and quantitative metrics derived from prior research studies documenting farming practices, losses, transport costs, and production challenges. This step will serve as the foundation for the subsequent processes in the research.

Building on the collected data, the analytic model is implemented to identify choke points within the supply chain using key variables. The key variables for simulating the pineapple supply chain in Camarines Norte can be categorized into five key variables: production, processing, distribution, pricing, and environmental. The production of Queen pineapple in Camarines Norte influences the yield,

demand, and pricing. Farm location, particularly in municipalities like Labo, affects logistics and transport costs. Farming practices, ranging from traditional to modern techniques affect productivity levels. Processing involves turning pineapples into dried pineapple, juice, and fibers from peel and eyes, with production volumes influenced by facility capacity and equipment efficiency. Distribution is associated with logistics, including transport and costs, impacting the efficiency of distribution to locality. Pricing, which is determined by size and weight, averages around ₱4 per kilogram. Profit distribution often favors traders, reducing farmer earnings. Despite these challenges, the Queen pineapple is highly resilient to weather conditions and is adapted to the soil of Camarines Norte and able to withstand extreme weather up to Tropical Cyclone Wind Signal (TCWS) 3. [4][7][8].

For the simulation model, the researchers have used the AnyLogic Software. Anylogic is a simulation software that supports different modeling paradigms. This includes Agent-Based Modeling (ABM) and Discrete Event Simulation (DES) that is used for this research to simulate the Queen pineapple supply chain by modeling different variables such as farmers, retailers, transporters, etc. and their interactions with ABM while using DES to simulate time-dependent processes such as harvesting, transportation, and processing. The results are used to identify the goals of the research such as inefficiencies and bottlenecks that could provide insights for the stakeholders.

Simulation Paradigm

A simulation framework based on ABM and DES to define the relationships and dependencies among key variables. This framework models and connects the interaction between variables such as production yield, processing capacity, transport efficiency, and profit distribution.

Figure 1: AnyLogic Simulation Paradigm for ABM and DES

IV. RESULT

Simulation Analysis

The simulation analysis provides insights and predictions based on the results of ABM and DES that is implemented by AnyLogic. The main focus of this analysis is to provide data that can be used to enhance supply chain efficiency and sustainability. Different graphs have been used to visualize and provide information for the researchers. Each graph represents different variables.

The Supply and Demand consists of variables that track the demand and supply of pineapples over time, with time as the independent variable that controls the value of demand, supply, and price fluctuations. The price reflects the changes in the cost of pineapple over the simulation period. The Pineapple Yield graph consists of variables such as base yields which refers to the yield of pineapple in 2023[1][6], and final yield, which is the predicted yield data at the end of the year. The current yield is the yield for every day passed in the simulation. It also includes the harvest loss and growth rate percentage which came from data [1]. The graph also incorporates yearly data that increments after 365 simulation days, days to mature which is a random value ranging from 15-18 months [8], and information on the locality yield for Camarines Norte. Process Products consist of types and volumes of processed items which includes pineapple juice, dried pineapple candy, and excess fruit material. The Pineapple used graph visualizes the number of raw materials used to create processed products and the total numbers of pineapple used to create raw materials. Lastly, the Farmer and Trader graph details the sales of various stakeholders which tracks the total sold juice and dried pineapple of traders and the sold fruit of farmers to traders. It also shows the year when these transactions occur which give insights of the timeline of trade activities throughout the simulated years.

The simulation yields numerical results which describe the status of queen pineapple supply chain in Camarines Norte. For instance, in the first run of the simulation, the researchers simulated the first 5 years since 2023 from initial data[6] and the result shows that the Pineapple Yield increases with a growth rate of 5.4% and harvest loss of 47.81% [1].

Year	2024	2025	2026	2027	2028
Yield Prediction (tonnes)	92.44	89.31	120.17	121.77	115.45
For Locality (tonnes)	6.2	6.78	8.69	8.03	8.11

Table 2.1 Pineapple Yield

The table 2.1 shows from 2024 to 2028 the simulation predicted the final yields were 92.44t, 89.31t, 120.17t, 121.77t, and 115.45t respectively. This demonstrates the rise and fall of yield throughout the simulated years. 10% of these final yields will go to local markets and processing facilities which will be used to manufacture products such as pineapple juice and dried pineapple. In this instance, the number of pineapples that will go into local production would be 6.2t, 6.78t, 8.69t, 8.03t, and 8.11t from 2024 to 2028.

The simulation for pineapple yield signifies that factors such as harvest loss and growth rate played a significant role in the variability of yields over time. From 2024 to 2028, the 5 simulation years predicted that the yield of pineapples were 92.44t, 89.31t, 120.17t, 121.77t, and

115.45t, respectively. These fluctuations indicate a growth and loss pattern which is also influenced by the maturity period of Queen pineapples. The high percentage of harvest loss of 47.81% signifies the need for interventions to minimize the loss through improved harvesting techniques and other strategies. Harvesting is the most important phase which needs to be carried with maximum efficiency. Harvesting techniques such as timing of the harvest, systematic sorting and cleaning, and proper handling can lead to reduced post-harvest loss [9]. The final yield only allocates 10% for the local markets and processing facilities signifies the importance of balancing the raw supply that revolves in the province to ensure that production to both market needs and processing demands within the locality of Camarines Norte are met [11].

Product	Quantity
Pineapple Juice	37,764 pouches
Dried Pineapple	1,800 pouches
Pineapple Fruit (excess)	6,787 pieces

Table 2.2 Processed Pineapple

Table 2.2 shows the pineapples had been used to produce 37,764 pouches of Pineapple Juice and 1,800 pouches of Dried Pineapple then the remaining 6,787 pineapples were not used in the processing over the course of 5 simulation years.

The processed pineapples over the 5 simulation years from 2024 to 2028 showed that resource utilization makes a significant increase in the number of pineapples processed rising from 23,520 to 121,520. This showed the growing demand for processed pineapple products highlighting the importance of investing in processing facilities to meet future market demands efficiently. Investments especially for agro-industrialists are essential for expanding the value chains by integrating not just facilities but more farmers, suppliers, and consumers or by increasing the volume and variety of products being exchanged results in reduced costs, minimized loss and waste, and improved product quality [10].

Year	Trader Sales (₱)	Farmer Sales (₱)
2024	10,213,492	335,459,451
2025	7,651,608	324,089.523
2026	14,615,088	441,005.048
2027	12,414,516	436,067.49
2028	13,242,980	418,962.867

Table 2.3 Farmer and Trader Sales

Furthermore, data from table 2.3 shows that the profit of traders depends on the sales of processed pineapple products and pineapple fruits while the farmers' profit solely depends on pineapple fruits at farm gate price. In this instance, the traders' profit ranges approximately from ₱9,440,580 pesos to ₱13,242,980 pesos. On the other hand, the farmers' profit ranges approximately from ₱399,395 pesos to ₱418,962 pesos from 2024 to 2028.

From the results of the simulation for farmers and traders, the simulation revealed a significant profit difference in both parties. This disparity signifies equity concerns within the supply chain. This imbalance could discourage farmer participation as their low earnings may not justify their efforts and investments. Other studies recommend that this should be addressed through better market policies, improved storage facilities, and the formation of farmer-based organizations that could help to enhance farmer participation and profitability [12].

Variable	Value
Demand	4,826,719 pineapples
Supply	3,976,448 pineapples
Days	6,150
Price	₱ 4.00

Table 2.4 Supply and Demand

Finally, table 2.4 shows the expected supply and demand of queen pineapple in 5 simulation years, which is straightforward and gradually increases and decreases through the course of time from 2024 to 2028 with the total demand of 3,986,036 and total supply of 3,280,588 in 2028.

Using the data from simulation, the researchers can identify and give insights where the bottlenecks and where aspects to improve in the supply chain.

The gradual fluctuations of supply and demand chain for 5 simulation years provided insight on how the supply was behind the demand. This gap signifies the need for interventions to boost the production and minimize the harvest loss to ensure the market stability [10].

The simulation results provided insights for the queen pineapple supply chain. The key bottlenecks in the supply chain include the high percentage of harvest loss and limited processing capacity which both need intervention to address this issue. Recommended solutions are investing in infrastructure and the adoption of modern farming techniques [10]. The significant difference between the profit of farmers and traders suggests a need for fair profit distribution. The recommendations for these are better market policies, improved storage facilities, and the formation of farmer-based organizations that could help to enhance farmer participation and profitability [12]. Lastly, the supply and demand gap indicates the need for improving the production and the reduction of inefficiencies in transport and processing, with the addition of expanding

the processing facilities to potentially reduce the excess and increase the product availability [9].

These insights through simulation can help the stakeholders to implement strategies to enhance the efficiency, equity, and sustainability of the queen pineapple supply chain in Camarines Norte.

V. CONCLUSION

This simulation study aimed to identify critical aspects, assess inefficiencies, and propose actionable strategies for improvement through the use of simulation tool AnyLogic and utilizing the Agent-Based Model (ABM) and Discrete Event Simulation (DES). The simulation provided valuable insights of efficiency and sustainability of the queen pineapple supply chain in Camarines Norte. The key findings showed fluctuations in pineapple yield in the course of 5 simulation years from 2024 to 2028 and were influenced by harvest loss, growth rate, and maturity days. Despite the fluctuations, the supply chain showed an ability to cope with increasing demands for processed products like pineapple juice and dried pineapple. Resource utilization increased from 23,520 to 121,520 pineapples during the simulation period. The supply and demand analysis showed a consistent gap throughout the simulation years but the gap is manageable suggesting the importance of improving the production processing and transport efficiency to balance the supply with growing demand. In profit distribution between farmers and traders, the traders benefit significantly more than the farmers signifying the need for strategies to enhance farmer earnings.

In conclusion, the major factor that affects the overall inefficiency of the supply chain of Queen pineapple in Camarines Norte is the high percentage of harvest loss which is a critical factor. With the use of simulation and the data through studies and interviews, the researchers have reached this conclusion. The findings indicate that post-harvest losses, which can reach as high as 47.81%, severely impact the availability of pineapples for processing and sale, resulting in the supply-demand gap. This inefficiency not only diminishes the potential profits for farmers but also affects the profitability of traders, leading to an imbalance in earnings across the supply chain. Addressing this issue through improved post-harvest handling practices, investment in processing facilities, and the adoption of modern agricultural techniques is recommended. By mitigating harvest losses, stakeholders can enhance the sustainability and profitability of the queen pineapple supply chain, ultimately benefiting all parties involved.

This simulation study contributes to understanding the queen pineapple supply chain in Camarines Norte and offers a replicable framework that can be used for future studies for diagnosing supply chain inefficiencies in other crops. The findings serve as an insight for the stakeholders to implement strategies aimed at improving the livelihood of farmers, optimizing the use of resources, and enhancing the overall quality and sustainability of the supply chain.

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